

WORKPLACE BULLYING, PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS, JOB SATISFACTION AND LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG TEACHERS: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

This study was conducted to explore the relationship between workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction among teachers across Sialkot City. The study was investigated to determine the impact of workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction on each other among personnel of different organizations. The sample of 270 participants was selected through convenience sampling technique. The Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R) was translated into Urdu language by following the World Health Organization (WHO) translation procedure and Urdu versions of Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS- 21), Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) and Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) was administered to measure the responses of the participants. The results of the study revealed a positive correlation between workplace bullying and psychological distress, and between job satisfaction and life satisfaction whereas, a negative relationship between workplace bullying and job satisfaction, also between workplace bullying and life satisfaction. The study was found a negative correlation between psychological distress and job satisfaction, between psychological distress and life satisfaction as well. The results of the study showed that workplace bullying was a strong predictor of psychological distress and job satisfaction is a strong predictor of life satisfaction. The research findings also indicated that workplace bullying and psychological distress was negatively predicted to job satisfaction and life satisfaction. The findings from this study could be useful for improvement of workers' mental health and increase their job and life satisfaction and also beneficial in developing better work environment in any working sector.

INTRODUCTION

Bullying can be initiated by anyone at any time against anybody as and when the gaps of performance are observed and breaches of discipline are noticed. This may include bullying incidents of harsh treatment, use of abusive language, verbal and

physical coercion, humiliating, scolding, teasing, harassing, adverse comments and negative castigation by decision makers, organizational heads and owners to workers, parents and teachers to children or students, superiors to subordinates, subordinates to

superiors and among co-workers as well (Fox & Spector, 2005; Neuman, 2004; Lee, 2002; Vartia, 2001). Resultantly the complete gamut of thoughtfulness gets disturbed and the victims start feeling the pinch of bullying both at mental as well as physical level (Gupta, 2013; De Vos & Kirsten, 2015).

According to the Erdogan (1997) and Fitzgerald (1972), almost every working person spends 70% life or 2/3rd portion of his life at the workplace (Demirel, 2014). Hence, workplace significantly impacts on workers' life both at physical and psychological levels. The social relationships and bonds of kinship are equally influenced by the workplace milieu. It is somewhat hard to mention that the life of an employee is highly committed, with the hard schedule and hectic working routine. In this vigorous but repetitive timetable, workers face numerous negatively charged situations and antisocial behavior displayed by their own workfellows, co-workers, supervisors, and others at the workplace on irregular and intermittent intervals, which adversely influence their physical as well as mental health (Tolentino, 2016). At the workplace, they experience many psychological problems like frustration, precinct of rules and restraints of system, stress, anxiety, and depression which may lead to hazardous consequences, including low levels of job satisfaction and life satisfaction. Ayoko et al., (2003), suggested that employees at workplace experience a range of physical and psychological symptoms such as work stress, anxiety, lowered job satisfaction and loyalty to the organization, increase in absenteeism, reduced work productivity and enhanced level of depression.

At the workplace, negative acts including bullying create psychological hazards all over the world. Almost every field of the life likely doctors, bankers, rescue, nurses, factory employees, police and teachers are affected by these negative actions. In any institute bullying is related to the employees' performance, loyalty, retention, and production of the organization (Sofield & Salmond, 2003). Present study focused on personnel of educational organizations like teachers have been targeted to explain employee's interaction with this bullying environment. **Workplace Bullying:** Bullying is an antisocial behavior which is faced by almost every

working individual. In the earliest studies, students were targeted as central part of bullying researches in which most attention was paid to the harassment of the students but some researchers realized that not only students but also the working people are the victims of bullying (Field, 2007). So that in early 1990s, first time academic community was interested to investigate the term of workplace bullying as a research topic with performance, wellbeing, and health of workers (Hoel, Rayner & Cooper, 1999). Adams (1992) coined the term workplace bullying and according to him workplace bullying is the workplace behavior of ongoing harassment between employees and it can result into negative outcomes from the targeted employees (Georgakopoulos, Wilkin & Kent, 2011). In mid-1980s, workplace bullying was recognized as a major work stressor. Nowadays bullying is transformed as major hazard at workplace and has become as the most interesting topic for researchers. Numerous researchers defined bullying in many perspectives but at workplace it becomes more difficult to define bullying because it is considered as umbrella term that contains not only one phenomenon but more than one (Hoel, Cooper, Faragher, 2001).

Many alternative terms are used to describe similar phenomenon of workplace bullying in several studies. Such as mobbing, harassment or work harassment, herd aggressive behavior, harassing behavior at workplace, non-sexual harassment, psychological harassment, victimization, psychological terror, employee abuse, emotional abuse, incivility, workplace violence, workplace negligence, workplace mistreatment, status blind harassment and workplace aggression all these are the indicative terms of workplace bullying. (Adebayo & Juliet, 2014; Charilaos et al., 2015; Einarsen et al., 2011; Giorgi, Arenas & M. Leon-Perez, 2011; Pinkos & Cobb, 2012). Many researchers investigate workplace bullying by using various terms mentioned above with specific rationale of their study. The term workplace bullying was used to explain the behavior for the determination of this study.

Like the numerous indicative terms, quite a lot of workplace bullying definitions are there but most appropriate and acceptable definition given by Einarsen et al, (1994), that it is a situation in which the target is unable to defend himself/herself from

persistence negative acts by a person or an organization for a specific period of time (Ikanyon & Ucho, 2013). In 2001, Einarsen and his colleagues further improved the existing definition of workplace bullying as a situation in which someone should be displeasing or annoyed, socially omitted or isolated, exclude from work or social circle, and often harassed frequently (weekly) for a specific sustainable time span (about six months) which affects his/her work performance negatively (Charilaos et al., 2015). Sometimes the concept of conflict and bullying are mixed together but Salin (2003), explained that they are distinguishing from each other according to its frequency and longevity of actions. While Einarsen et al., (2003), stated that an isolated event in which two equal powerful parties are involved is called conflict not bullying. Furthermore, Olsen (2010), distinguished the four main elements of workplace bullying behavior including (1) unwanted (annoying or undesirable), (2) unwarranted (unnecessary or unjustified), (3) repeated (frequent or constant) and (4) detrimental behavior (negative or adverse behaviors). The conduct of such behaviors is injurious for a civilized society (Adebayo & Juliet, 2014).

Types of Workplace Bullying: On the basis of above mentioned categories of bullying behavior the workplace bullying was divided into two main types including person-related bullying and work-related bullying (Einarsen & Hoel, 2001; Beswick, Gore & Palferman, 2006). Details are mentioned below: -

Personal Bullying. Personal bullying is considered as a stress which has negative impact on employees' well-being, change or makes variations in personality and mood, leading possible psychophysical indications and also psychiatric complaints like post-traumatic stress, chronic adjustment, and anxiety-depression disorder. Similarly humiliating openly, embarrassing publically, avoiding or disregarding purposely, insulting, interfering the victim's privacy and shouting on the victim are the most commonly observed behaviors in person-related bullying (Beswick, Gore & Palferman, 2006).

Work-related Bullying. Although work-related bullying associate to aggressive behavior which is focused on the victim's work like safety intimidation,

withholding information from the victim that eventually affect victim's performance, assigning impossible or difficult targets and jobs etc. At workplace people most commonly experience these types of behaviors from time to time (Beswick, Gore & Palferman, 2006; Einarsen & Hoel, 2001).

Major Reasons Behind Workplace Bullying. There can be any reason for workplace bullying, however, intrinsic characteristics / traits of victim is also the possible reasons for such bullying. In 2003, Zapf and Einarsen explained three main reasons for workplace bullying that makes a person the target of bullying in the workplace. The victim has low confidence, low self-esteem, low social capability, and has no companions in the group (Georgakopoulos, Wilkin & Kent, 2011). Furthermore, micro-political behavior contributes bullying at the workplace, in which one person was defending his/her position by taking selfish decisions that are beneficial for himself/herself but harmful for others' status or repute in the organization. Organizational culture and power imbalances are workplace bullying the reasons which lead to workplace bullying (Salin, 2003).

Bullying Process at Workplace: Einarsen (2005), described the process of bullying in some phases, in which initially indirect and discrete form of behavior prevail that later on seems to be more direct hostile actions. The target was insulated, withdrawn and avoided or ignored, humiliate openly by being the Laughingstock at the workplace. In this bullying process, both physical and psychological violence should be used. Targets of long-term bullying often attacked more than those targets that have the shorter history of bullying. In the initial phase, targets were attacked rarely and when the situation escalates the occurrence of bullying incidents become more regular and cruel and later aggressive action against target was taken on weekly or even daily basis.

Psychological Distress: For thousands of years, the presence of psychological distress at the workplace was acknowledged by many researchers. Many job-related studies demonstrate typical cases of psychologically distressed man, in which he loses his interest once he likes to do, have sleep problems, self-

depreciating, blame himself, and become introverted, depressed or downhearted. Approximately 3, 900 years ago the ancient Egyptian manuscript draws a perfect picture of a distressed person. In which person become pessimistic or suspicious, losing his trust on others, have difficulty in everyday functioning, and thoughts of suicide. These historical explanations corresponds the current psychological distress phenomenon. For many years psychological distress is a controversial phenomenon that is difficult to explain but scientific literature indicates that psychological distress is a frequent application of the identical mixture of depression and general anxiety symptoms fluctuating towards personality traits, functional disabilities, and behavioral problems (Shaheen, 2013). The major features of psychological distress are disclosure a stressful incident that intimidates physical or mental health, the incompetence to cope successfully with this stressor and the consequences of demonstrative confusion appears due to this ineffective coping (Horwitz, 2007; Ridner, 2004). However, Wheaton (2007), argued that psychological distress is the disturbance with emotions that influence the individual's social functioning and everyday living, which is clearly described by symptoms of depression and anxiety (Drapeau, Marchand & Beaulieu-Prévost, 2012).

Job Satisfaction: Job satisfaction is an important part of employee lives. If employees are highly satisfied with their job then they enjoy their job, their physical and psychological health was improved, they become more motivated, they perform work in more efficient and effective manner and production was increased of the organization, which is not only constructive for their personal and professional success but also important for a healthy and successful society. Job satisfaction is generally a multidimensional concept that was only addressed in the 1930s and 1940s but later several sub-disciplines of social sciences paid a significant attention on this concept. Erdamar and Demirel (2016), stated that individual generally feel happy and successful when he/she was satisfied with what he/she does and this state of satisfaction is defined as job satisfaction. Generally, job satisfaction is thoroughly related to a person's behavior at the workplace. A sense of

achievement and success of a person about his/her job is considered as the job satisfaction. However, nowadays Spector's definition of job satisfaction is most widely used by the researchers where job satisfaction has to do with a manner to find what individuals should feel about their jobs and its different aspects. It also has to do with the degree to which person liking and disliking his/her job (Aziri, 2011).

Life Satisfaction: Life satisfaction is an overall feeling of fulfillment or achievement regarding to an individual's life goals that he/she set for him/her-self and about his/her expectations from his/her own life. In 1961, Neugarten was the first person who introduced the concept of life satisfaction that is referred as a condition or result attained through a comparison of what an individual wants to have and what he/she actually has (Ozer & Karabulut, 2003). Neugarten operationally defined life satisfaction as successful aging (Demirel, 2014).

According to Diener and Biswas-Diener (2008), life satisfaction is a measuring instrument of well-being, which determined by the good performance in major areas of life like social relations, physical and mental health, work, revenue, religiousness, and leisureliness (Ignat & Clipa, 2012). Life satisfaction does not belong with the extent of days we live, but in the use, we make of these days. A person who may live long yet might bring little from life. Therefore, life satisfaction depends on the determination of a person not on the number of days or years. In the judgment of life satisfaction, a person set a standard which he/she recognized proper for conditions of lives (Abdullah & Mushtaq, 2015).

Resentfully, the affective theory suggested that life satisfaction is to be a person's attentive or certain experience as the supremacy of his/her positive emotions on his/her negative emotions. The latest research showed that life satisfaction is considered as the magnitude of the positive emotions experienced by a person (Prasoon & Chaturvedi, 2016; Simsek, 2011).

Literature Review

The roots of bullying phenomenon are linked with the behavior of an animal group and childhood bullying that establishes its own terms and meanings.

In 1980s, Leymann was first person who recognized the bullying concept in terms of mobbing. Leymann grabbed the term of mobbing from different studies to explain the phenomenon of group aggression in which the groups of aggressive and powerful animals' ganging up against weaker animals. Powerful animal deploy to gain status and power in their societies—in a manner which is strikingly similar to how humans behave at work and at war. After perceived bullying behavior of a children group, Leymann applied his studies at the workplace and found that bullying as an abuse negatively impacts upon the mental health of workers (Taylor, 2012).

When people have been working together workplace bullying is an indication that should have the effect on the job satisfaction, job performance and other attitudes of workers. The workplace consequences also affect the workers psychological and physical health that has been thoroughly acknowledged in the scholarly literature. In this regards a research is conducted by Quine (2001), in UK to determine the frequency of bullying and its effects on nurses, the research results showed that the bullied nurses reported high levels of depression, anxiety, and tendency to quit, while the level of their job satisfaction was substantially low. Some other studies correspondingly described that bullying having psychological and physical sickness, job dissatisfaction, exclusion from marketplace, declined commitment and low production, high level of absenteeism, turnover and intention to resign (Hoel & Cooper, 2000; Hoel et al., 2003; Keashly & Jagatic, 2003; Vartia, 2001). Moreover, several researches indicated that the victims of workplace bullying have a wide range of physical and psychological indications such as work strain, anxiety, depression, decrease job satisfaction and least devotion to institute, dropped the work productivity and higher absenteeism (Ayoko et al, 2003). Similarly, the findings of the Glaso, Nielsen, Einarsen, Haugland, and Matthiesen, (2009), research disclosed that the individuals are considered as more tense and disturbed, introverted, disorganized and unreliable who were probably intimidated. In the same way Rockers (2008), stated that workplace bullying is a basic organizational problem that has an impact on the target of bullying in form of nausea, intoxication, and predispositions

of suicide sleeplessness, anxiety, depression, and loss of motivation (Yildiz, 2007).

Many studies investigated the relationship of workplace bullying with different variables such as stress, depression and reported a positive relationship with workplace bullying while negative relationship between self-esteem and workplace bullying was found (Blase & Blase, 2006; Cech, 2010; Djurkovic, 2004; Hoel & Cooper, 2000; Johnson, 2009; Matthiesen et al., 2003; Mikkelsen & Einarsen, 2001). Some researches revealed that the workplace bullying was negatively associated with job satisfaction (Bowling & Beehr, 2006; Rodríguez-Muñoz, Baillien, De Witte, Moreno-Jiménez, & Pastor, 2009). Subsequently, several researchers investigated the relationship between workplace bullying, job satisfaction and satisfaction with life and concluded that workplace bullying associated with low life satisfaction and results also showed that workplace bullying have different psychological problems such as post-traumatic stress disorder (Mikkelsen, & Einarsen, 2002), high level of anxiety, depression and work-related consequences such as, absenteeism, increase intent to quit and job dissatisfaction (Hauge, Skogstad, & Einarsen, 2010; Lutgen-Sandvik, Tracy, & Alberts, 2007; Djurkovic, McCormack, & Casimir, 2008). According to all these researchers, it was concluded that the workplace bullying firstly affected the psychological well-being of the victim in form of anxiety, depression, and stress that further leads the low job satisfaction and increase the intent to quit that additionally affects the overall life satisfaction of an individual.

For instance, Einarsen (2005), stated that the targets of bullying have high level of psychological distress, which may be due to the changes in target's perception about working environment and life generally in a threat, danger, insecurity, and self-questioning. Similarly, a research by Quine (2003), showed that the target of workplace bullying has the high level of psychological distress and low level of job satisfaction. The findings of Guckin, Lewis, Shevlin, and Prentice (2013), study disclosed that workplace bullying was a major source to decrease job and life satisfaction. In this regard, the study of Bernotaite and Malinauskiene (2017), revealed that

workplace bullying is the strong predictor of psychological distress among teachers. Similarly, the result of Samaranayake, Arroll, and Fernando (2014), research indicated that life satisfaction is positively correlated with health and negatively related to depression, anxiety, and loneliness. Moreover, in this aspect, the findings of some studies showed that life satisfaction is negatively associated with psychological distress (Stallman, 2010; Guney, Khalafat, & Boysan, 2010; Mahmood & Saleem, 2011; Dachew, Bisetegn, & Gebremariam, 2015).

The study of Fushimi (2012), showed that high level of job satisfaction associated with low level of psychological distress. The results of Koval's (2014), research revealed that psychological distress was positively related to workplace bullying and both of these affects the level job satisfaction of employees. In the same context, another research was conducted by Abdullah and Mushtaq (2015) that also indicated the negative relationship between psychological distress and life satisfaction. Furthermore, the research of Kumar, Shaheen, Rasool, and Shafi (2016), reported the same findings that the psychological distress is the significant predictor of the low level of life satisfaction. The research of Sharma and Garg (2016), showed that there was a negative relationship between life satisfaction and psychological distress when one increases the other was decreases. The study of Amati et al., (2010), found the negative relationship between job satisfaction and psychological distress.

The Rode's (2004), research concluded that job satisfaction has a significant effect on life satisfaction, if the level of job satisfaction high then the level of life satisfaction also increases. Keser (2005), stated that there was a positive relationship between job and life satisfaction. Some studies were also reported the similar results that job satisfaction are positively associated with life satisfaction (Avsaroglu, Deniz & Kahraman, 2005; Lent & Brown, 2006). Theodossior and Ioannis et al., (2006), stated that job satisfaction has a positive relationship with life satisfaction. Moreover, the study findings of Ignat and Clipa (2012), showed that life satisfaction is positively correlated with job satisfaction among teachers. The research by Erdamar and Demirel (2016), concluded that life satisfaction increases as job satisfaction increases.

Rationale of the Study

It has been generally observed that in the present era, the workplace has become more challenging, conspicuous and persistent fact that influences workers mentally, physically and socially. In this perspective bullying is a serious issue that mostly arises in the workplace and persuades mental conditions, affairs of job, and life of workers. In this context it becomes imperative for me as a researcher to find and investigate the phenomenon of bullying and its impact on mental health, job satisfaction and life satisfaction of employees, who are performing a highly sacred and most valuable job for our country's future.

Numerous studies have found and investigated the impact of bullying among different samples with various variables such as psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction but not a single study has been conducted to find and investigate the impact of bullying on seven different samples with regard to their job satisfaction and life satisfaction. Labors are considered as the most important part of Pakistani society. Every workplace is different than other therefore, the job satisfaction and level of life satisfaction of many working sectors appears to have been neglected by the researchers in Pakistan. Bullying no doubt, is one of the major problems that is faced by employees at the workplace that influence not only their mental health but also disturbs their personal and professional life. Employees, however, usually experience this problem at the workplace that further causes many other complications for them but they have not reported this issue and have remained silent. An effort has been made to finish the reticent attitude of workforces in Sialkot city who hesitate in openly discussing their ordeals connected with job satisfaction and life satisfaction. Hence this study has been planned to create deeper understanding about bullying of different employees at their workplace.

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the levels of bullying, psychological distress, job and life satisfaction among teachers and also find out their interrelationship in reference to Pakistani culture. In Pakistan, workplace bullying reported in many studies but not a single study was reported with psychological distress, job, and life satisfaction among different samples at the same time. So, there

is a gap in research field and this study should try to cover-up this major research gap by investigating the workplace bullying, psychological distress, job, and life satisfaction among teachers and highlight the nature and effects of workplace bullying in educational sector which contribute to helping workers for achieving and maintaining good mental health as well their job and life satisfaction.

The current study has been designed for implementing strategies and interventions to combat workplace bullying, psychological distress and

increase job satisfaction, life satisfaction among doctors, bankers, rescue, nurses, factory employees, police and teachers. Thus, this study is valuable to provide awareness about the possible preventions of workplace bullying and psychological distress to organizations, employees and the whole society as well. This study may also contribute to play a positive role to improve the employees' psychological health and increase their job and life satisfaction to make the organization system more effective.

Conceptual Framework

Methods

Objectives

The objectives of the research are as follows:

1. To find the levels of workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction among teachers across Sialkot City.
2. To explore whether or not intensity or frequency of workplace bullying had a greater impact on psychological distress, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction.
3. To investigate the interrelationship of workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City.

Hypothesis

After reviewing the literature following hypothesis were formulated:

1. There would be a significant correlation between workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction among teachers across Sialkot City.

2. Workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of psychological distress among teachers in Sialkot City.
3. Workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of job satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City.
4. Workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City.
5. Psychological distress would be the significant predictor of job satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City.
6. Psychological distress would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City.
7. Job satisfaction would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City.

Operational Definition of Variables

Workplace Bullying. Bullying at work means harassing, offending, socially excluding someone or

negatively affecting someone's work tasks. In order for the label bullying (or mobbing) to be applied to a particular activity, interaction or process it has to occur repeatedly and regularly (e.g. weekly) and over a period of time (e.g. about six months). Bullying is an escalated process in the course of which the person confronted ends up in an inferior position and becomes the target of systematic negative social acts (Einarsen, Hoel & Notelaers, 2009).

Psychological Distress. Psychological distress is the combine effect of depression, anxiety and stress. Psychological distress is an overall negative emotional state with the core symptoms of depression (e.g. dysphoria, hopelessness, devaluation of life, self-deprecation, lack of interest/involvement, anhedonia, and inertia), anxiety (e.g. autonomic arousal, skeletal muscle effects, situational anxiety, and subjective experience of anxious affect) and stress (e.g. difficulty relaxing, nervous arousal, and being easily upset/agitated, irritable/over-reactive and impatient) (Lovibond, S.H., & Lovibond, P.F., 1995).

Job Satisfaction. Job Satisfaction is that individual whose performance on nine dimensions i.e., pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, coworkers, nature of work and communication are satisfactory is said to be having job satisfaction (Spector, 1994).

Life Satisfaction. Life Satisfaction is overall feeling and attitudes i.e., desire to change one's life, satisfaction with past and future and significant other's views of one's life (Diener et al., 1985).

Research Design: The cross-sectional survey research design was used in this study.

Population and Sample

- a. The target population for the study was teachers of different public and private educational institutions (school, college, and university) across the Sialkot City
- b. The sample of the study was teachers of different public and private educational institutions (school, college, and university) across Sialkot City
- c. The age range of sample was 25-60 years with academic ranks i.e., professor, assistant

professor, associate professor, lecturers, primary and secondary school teachers

- d. The sample of 270 participants was selected in this study, through convenience sampling.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria. The inclusion criteria include the following: -

- a. The teaching staff of educational institutions with the required age range (25-60 years) was included in the study.
- b. Only the victims of bullying were included in the study.
- c. Willing participant teachers were included.

Exclusion Criteria. Exclusion criteria included the following aspects: -

- a. Teachers below the age of 25 years and above the age of 60 years were excluded from the study.
- b. Participant teachers who wished to discontinue or withdraw from the research study were excluded.
- c. Teachers who were not willing to participate were also excluded.

Measures: The following measurement tools were used in the research study: -

Consent Letter/Form. Consent form has the detail description about the research and request to the heads of institutions to permit the researcher to collect data from their institution. A copy of research questionnaire was attached with consent form that is provided to the concern authorities. Consent from was signed by the head of Institution and the respondent to confirm their participation.

Demographic Form. Participants also completed a demographic questionnaire. The questionnaire gathered data relative to participants' age, gender, marital status, socioeconomic status, Institution, academic rank, working status, department, and working experience.

The Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R; Einarsen, Hoel & Notelaers, 2009). To measure the workplace bullying Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R) developed by Einarsen, Hoel &

Notelaers in 2009 was used in this research. This inventory consists of 25 questionnaire and 22-items used to assess the workplace bullying while other 3 question give the description about the status of the participant as the victim of bullying, about the person by which the victim was bullied, about the gender and number of the perpetrator. The NAQ-R is constructed on the workplace bullying definition given by Einarsen et al., (2001). The NAQ-R was measure how often during the previous six months respondents has been subjected to various negative acts, which when occurred on a frequent basis might be considered as bullying (Mikkelsen, 2001). In NAQ-R the word bullying was not used that is the best part of the inventory because when the participants were answering the questionnaire they have not the perception of bullying during this. This scale was a 5-point Likert rating scale that reflects typical bullying behaviors and the participants should respond into the range from 1 (never), 2 (now and then), 3 (monthly), 4 (weekly) to 5 (daily). The NAQ-R scale has shown the sufficient reliability ranging from $\alpha.87$ to $\alpha.93$.

Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21; Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995). Lovibond and Lovibond (1995) were developed the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21) to assess psychological distress. The Urdu version of Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21) was used in the study that was translated by Aslam in 2007. This inventory has three subscales to measure psychological distress, first subscale should measure the depression (e.g. loss of self-esteem/incentives and depressed mood), second should assess the anxiety (e.g. fear and anticipation of negative events) and third would use to extend the stress (e.g. persistent state of over-arousal and low frustration tolerance). The scale was consisting of 21 items in which each subscale has seven items. It was a four-point rating self-reporting inventory in which participants were asked to rate how many of each of the statements applied to them over the past week with the response rate from Never (0), Sometimes (1), Often (2) to Almost always (3). The reliability of the scale was $\alpha.83$ and the alpha reliability coefficient of the subscales of DASS-21 was $\alpha.91$ to $\alpha.97$ for

Depression scale, $\alpha.81$ to $\alpha.92$ for Anxiety scale, and $\alpha.88$ to $\alpha.95$ for Stress scale.

Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS; Spector, 1997). The Urdu version of Spector's (1997) Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) was used to measure job satisfaction that is translated by Salman Shahzad in 2010. The Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) consists of 36 items containing nine subscales related to overall job satisfaction such as Pay, Promotion, Supervision, Fringe benefits, Contingent rewards, Operating conditions, Coworkers, Nature of work, and Communication; each subscale has 4 items. It is a six-point Likert scale in which respondent was responded the items from 1 (disagree very much) to 6 (agree very much). The coefficient alpha of JSS range was $\alpha.60$ to $\alpha.91$.

Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS; Diener, 1985). The Urdu version of Satisfaction with life scale (SWLS) developed by Diener et al., (1985) and translated by Mussafa in 2014 was used in the study. It was a seven-point Likert scale contains five items with the response rate of 1=strongly disagree to 7=strongly agree, that was intended to measure the global life satisfaction of the participant. The SWLS was reported high internal consistency with Cronbach's α values ranging between $\alpha.80$ and $\alpha.51$.

Procedure: Initially, permission of authors of all the research scales was sought, and then the Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R) was translated into Urdu language by following the standardized procedure of World Health Organization (WHO). This procedure has six steps of translation, at the first step; forward translation of the original version of NAQ-R collected by six translators that were translated NAQ-R in the Urdu language. After this step, an expert panel meeting was arranged in which experts give their suggestions and recommendations about all provided forms of translations and finalized in one form of forward translation that was given to an independent translator for backward translation and final version of translated NAQ-R was completed/formulated.

After this process, different public and private schools, colleges and universities of Sialkot city were approached with a consent letter for concerned

authorities of selected institutions and participants. After getting permission from authorities of concerned institutions, the purpose of the study was explained to the institutions heads and participants; it was assured to them the information was strictly kept confidential. Then self-developed demographic information sheet was administered as per requirement of this study. Then all research scales were administered. After data collection, all participants and authorities of concern institutions were thanked for their cooperation / voluntary participation in this research project.

Ethical Considerations

a. Respect for the dignity of research participants was prioritized.

b. Informed consent was obtained from the concerned authorities of the institutions and participants prior to the study.

c. Full confidentiality was assured to the participants.

d. Participants were given the right to withdraw from the study at will.

Results

Demographic Details

Table 1 contains the frequencies and percentage of the demographical characteristics of participants of the study along with the Mean and Standard Deviation of age. The sample is characterized with respect to age, gender, marital status, socioeconomic status, institution, basic pay scale, employment status, department and work experience that are described in this Table.

Table 1
Demographical Characteristics of Participants, (N=270)

Variables	F	%	M(SD)
Age			2.91 (1.91)
25 years to 30 years	97	(35.9)	
31 years to 35 years	43	(15.9)	
36 years to 40 years	35	(13.0)	
41 years to 45 years	24	(8.9)	
46 years to 50 years	36	(13.3)	
51 years to 55 years	24	(8.9)	
56 years to 60 years	11	(4.1)	
Gender			
Male	113	(41.9)	
Female	157	(58.1)	
Marital Status			
Unmarried	94	(34.8)	
Married	158	(58.5)	
Widower	15	(5.6)	
Divorced	3	(1.1)	
Socioeconomic Status			
Upper class	37	(13.7)	
Middle class	228	(84.4)	
lower class	5	(1.9)	
Institute			
School	100	(37.0)	
College	88	(32.6)	
University	82	(30.4)	
Basic Pay Scale			
BPS-14	39	(14.4)	
BPS-16	32	(11.9)	

BPS-17	36	(13.3)
BPS-18	52	(19.3)
BPS-19	61	(22.6)
BPS-20	25	(9.3)
BPS-21	25	(9.3)
Employment Status		
Permanent	135	(50.0)
Contract	110	(40.7)
Visiting	25	(9.3)
Department		
IT/Computer	40	(14.8)
Business	40	(14.8)
Arts/Social Sciences	98	(36.3)
Natural Sciences	56	(20.7)
Engineering	36	(13.3)
Work Experience		
Less than 1 years	36	(13.3)
1 years to 5 years	92	(34.1)
6 years to 10 years	55	(20.4)
11 years to 15 years	34	(12.6)
16 years to 20 years	30	(11.1)
Above 20 years	23	(8.5)

Note: Frequencies (f), Percentage (%), Mean (M), Standard Deviations (SD).

Table 1 demonstrated that participants mostly belong to age range from 25 to 30 with the frequency of 97 while only 11 participants were of the age of 56 to 60 years. The table illustrated that sample consisted of 41.9% males and 58.1% females. This table also described that 158 participants were married, 94 unmarried while 15 were the widowers and 3 participants were divorced. Furthermore, 84.4% of the sample belonged to the middle class, 13.7% from upper class and only 1.9% has the low socioeconomic status in the study. The study contains 100 school participants, 88 respondents from the college and 82 from the universities across

the Sialkot city. With the respect of basic pay scale (BPS), the highest percentage was reported by the participants of the BPS-19 that is 22.6% and the lowest percentage is 9.3% that was reported by the respondents of BPS-20 and BPS-21. On the basis of employment status, only 135 participants have the status of permanent job while 110 were on the contract basis and 25 were on visiting role. This Table also described that 14.8% of the sample belonged to IT/computer and business departments, 36.3% from arts/social sciences, 20.7% from natural sciences while almost 13.3% from engineering department. The Table showed that mostly participants have 1 to 5 years of work experience that is the 34.1% of the sample.

Table 2
Psychometric properties of the study variables (N=270)

Variables	N	M	SD	α	Range		Skewness
					Potential	Actual	
NAQ-R	22	50.27	17.88	.93	1-5	1.607 - 3.296	.61
DASS-21	21	22.39	9.93	.87	0-3	.774 - 1.430	.24
JSS	36	126.38	20.46	.80	1-6	2.507 - 4.448	.38
SWLS	5	16.33	6.42	.83	1-7	2.248 - 3.963	.70

Note: Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R), Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21), Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS), Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS), Number of scale items (N), Means (M), Standard Deviations (SD), Cronbach Alpha Coefficients (α).

Table 2 showed the number of items in each scale, means, standard deviations, alpha reliabilities, potential and actual range of research scales. The skewness values of all scales are given less than 1 which showed the normality of research data. This table also illustrated the alpha reliability coefficient for Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R) which is ($\alpha=.93$). The Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21) has the value of $\alpha=.87$ for alpha reliability, and for Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) alpha value is $\alpha=.80$, while Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) alpha value range is $\alpha=.83$.

Hypothesis 1

The first hypothesis stated that there would be a significant correlation between workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction among teachers across Sialkot City. The data was analyzed employing Pearson Correlation Coefficient and the results (table 3), indicate that a significant positive relationship between workplace bullying and psychological distress ($r =.62, p < .01$) and a significant negative correlation between workplace bullying and job satisfaction ($r =-.49, p < .01$), significant association between life satisfaction and workplace bullying ($r =-.30, p < .01$), was found. Similarly psychological distress is negatively related to job satisfaction and life satisfaction ($r =-.43, r =-.33, p < .01$). While job satisfaction is positively associated with life satisfaction ($r =.34, p < .01$). These finding supported the first hypothesis of the research study. The Null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3

Correlation Matrix for main variables of the Study (N=270)

Variables	1	2	3	4	M	SD
1.Workplace Bullying	–	.62**	-.49**	-.30**	50.27	17.88
2.Psychological Distress		–	-.43**	-.33**	22.39	9.92
3. Job Satisfaction			–	.34**	126.38	20.46
4. Life Satisfaction				–	16.33	6.42

Note: Means (M), Standard Deviations (SD).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Hypothesis 2

The second hypothesis stated that workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of psychological distress among teachers in Sialkot City. In order to test the hypothesis linear regression analysis was conducted. The results (table 4) suggested that workplace bullying is significant predictor of psychological distress. The R^2 indicated 39% of

variance in the score for psychological distress can be accounted for by independent variable entered in the analysis with $F(1, 269)= 175.87, p<.001$. Moreover, results showed that there is significant impact of workplace bullying on psychological distress ($\beta = .62, t = 13.26, p < .001$). These findings supported the second hypothesis of the research study.

Table 4

Linear Regression Analysis for Workplace Bullying as Predictor of Psychological Distress (N = 270)

Variables	R^2	β	t	F (Model)
Constant	.39		3.43	175.87***
Psychological Distress		.62	13.26***	

*** $p < .001, df = (1, 269)$

Hypothesis 3

The third hypothesis stated that workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of job satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. The data was analyzed using linear regression in which workplace bullying as an independent variable significantly predicted job satisfaction the outcome variable. Results (table 5) R² indicated 24% of variance in the score for overall job satisfaction of teachers can be

accounted for by independent variable entered in the analysis with F (1, 269) = 88.25, p<.001. Results given in this Table revealed that there is significant effect of workplace bullying on overall job satisfaction ($\beta = -.49, t = -9.39, p < .001$). Moreover, in the findings of this table, workplace bullying was found as a negative predictor of job satisfaction. The results supported the third hypothesis of the research study.

Table 5

Linear Regression Analysis for Workplace Bullying as Predictor of Job Satisfaction (N = 270)

Variables	R ²	β	t	F (Model)
Constant	.24		47.93	88.25***
Job Satisfaction		-.49	-9.39***	

***p <.001, df = (1, 269)

Hypothesis 4

The fourth hypothesis stated that workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. In order to test the hypothesis linear regression analysis was employed. The results (table 6) show that workplace bullying significantly predict the variable of life satisfaction. The R² showed 9% of variance in the score for life satisfaction of teachers can be accounted for by

independent variable entered in the analysis with F (1, 269) = 26.41, p<.001. The findings of the table revealed that there is significant impact of workplace bullying on life satisfaction ($\beta = -.30, t = -5.13, p < .001$). Results of this Table indicated that workplace bullying was a negative predictor of life satisfaction. These findings supported the fourth hypothesis of the study.

Table 6

Linear Regression Analysis for Workplace Bullying as Predictor of Life Satisfaction (N = 270)

Variables	R ²	β	t	F (Model)
Constant	.09		19.46	26.41***
Life Satisfaction		-.30	-5.13***	

***p <.001, df = (1, 269)

Hypothesis 5

The fifth hypothesis stated that psychological distress would be the significant predictor of job satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. Linear regression was used to test the hypothesis. The results (table 7) demonstrated that psychological distress was

significant predictor of job satisfaction. Results suggested 19% of the variance in the score for job satisfaction with F (1, 269) = 63.29, p<.001. Findings further showed that there is a negative impact of psychological distress on job satisfaction ($\beta = -.43, t=-7.95, P<.001$). The fifth hypothesis of the research study was supported by these findings.

Table 7

Linear Regression Analysis for Psychological Distress as Predictor of Job satisfaction (N = 270)

Variables	R ²	β	t	F (Model)
Constant	.19		52.85	63.29***
Job satisfaction		-.43	-7.95***	

***p <.001, df = (1, 269)

Hypothesis 6

The sixth hypothesis stated that psychological distress would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. The hypothesis was tested using linear regression analysis. In this analysis psychological distress was entered as the predictor variable and life satisfaction as outcome variable. The R² showed 10% of variance in the score for life satisfaction of teachers can be

accounted for by independent variable entered in the analysis with $F(1, 269) = 32.84, p < .001$. The findings of Table 8 shown that there is significant impact of psychological distress on life satisfaction ($\beta = -.33, t = -5.73, p < .001$). Results given in this table demonstrated that psychological distress was a negative predictor of life satisfaction. The findings supported the sixth hypothesis of the research study.

Table 8

Linear Regression Analysis for Psychological Distress as Predictor of Life Satisfaction (N = 270)

Variables	R ²	B	t	F (Model)
Constant	.10		23.11	32.84***
Life satisfaction		-.33	-5.73***	

***p <.001, df = (1, 269)

Hypothesis 7

The seventh hypothesis stated that job satisfaction would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. The data was analyzed using linear regression analysis. The results (table 9) showed the impact of job satisfaction on life satisfaction. The R² displayed 11% of variance in

the score of overall life satisfaction $F(1, 269) = 36.02, p < .001$. Findings of this table show that there is significant effect of job satisfaction on overall life satisfaction ($\beta = .34, t = 6.00, p < .001$). Results supported the seventh hypothesis of the research study.

Table 9

Linear Regression Analysis for Job Satisfaction as Predictor of Life Satisfaction (N = 270)

Variables	R ²	B	t	F (Model)
Constant	.11		1.15	36.02***
Life satisfaction		.34	6.00***	

***p <.001, df = (1, 269)

Discussion

The present study was designed (a) To find the levels of workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City; (b) To explore whether or not intensity or frequency of workplace bullying had a greater impact on psychological distress, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction; (c) To investigate the interrelationship of workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction among teachers across Sialkot City. In order to achieve these objectives it was hypothesized that (a) There would be a significant correlation between workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction among teachers across Sialkot City;

(b) Workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of psychological distress among teachers in Sialkot City; (c) Workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of job satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City; (d) Workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City; (e) Psychological distress would be the significant predictor of job satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City; (f) Psychological distress would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City; (g) Job satisfaction would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City; and (h) There would be a significant difference between workplace bullying,

psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction according to demographical variables (i.e., gender, age, marital status, academic rank and departments) among teachers across Sialkot City. These hypotheses were tested employing correlation coefficient, t test, linear regression and one way ANOVA. Details are discussed in the following paragraphs: -

Correlation between Workplace Bullying, Psychological Distress, Job Satisfaction and Life Satisfaction:

Our first hypothesis stated that there would be a significant correlation between workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction among teachers across Sialkot City. The results (table 3) show that there was a significant relationship between workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction. Positive relationship has been found between workplace bullying and psychological distress ($r = .62, p < .01$), and between job satisfaction and life satisfaction ($r = .34, p < .01$). These results supported our hypothesis. Charilaos et al., (2015), stated that when workplace bullying increases the level of psychological distress also increases and if the level of job satisfaction increases the life satisfaction will also increase. Similarly Bernotaite and Malinauskiene (2017), supported this finding stating that workplace bullying and psychological distress was positively related to each other. Banerjee (2015), suggested that there was a positive relationship between job satisfaction and life satisfaction. As similar findings were reported by the study of Alghamdi (2015), that both job and life satisfaction goes hand to hand. Another research by Erdamar and Demirel (2016), directed that life satisfaction increases when job satisfaction increase.

On other hand results of correlation analysis showed that there was a negative correlation between workplace bullying and job satisfaction ($r = -.49, p < .01$) and between life satisfaction ($r = -.30, p < .01$) as well as psychological distress negatively associated with job satisfaction and life satisfaction ($r = -.43, r = -.33, p < .01$). Ikyanyon and Ucho (2013), reported that workplace bullying has negative relationship with job satisfaction. Similarly Carroll and Lauzier (2014), found that the level of job satisfaction will decreased when the workplace bullying increased.

Francis (2014), stated that the high level of workplace bullying should decrease the degree of job satisfaction. The research of Gupta (2013), concluded that workplace bullying has the negative relationship with life satisfaction. Visinskaite (2015), stated that life satisfaction becomes low when workplace bullying is high. Malik & Bano (2016), suggested that there was negative association between life satisfaction and workplace bullying. Abdullah and Mushtaq (2015), investigated the relationship of psychological distress and life satisfaction and explored a negative relationship between them. Sharma and Garg (2016), demonstrated that level of life satisfaction will decrease when the psychological distress increases. A similar finding was reported by the study of Kumar et al., (2016), that psychological distress was negatively associated with life satisfaction. The findings of Quine's (2003) research showed a negative relationship between workplace bullying and psychological distress with job satisfaction. Another study by Taylor (2012), stated that workplace bullying was a major source of job dissatisfaction among employee. Similarly, the study of Okwaraji and Aguwa (2015), reported that job satisfaction was negatively associated with workplace bullying and psychological distress. The research of Amati et al., (2010), stated that psychological distress was negatively associated with job satisfaction. In this regard, research findings Manzoor et al., (2011), demonstrated that psychological distress was negatively correlated with job satisfaction. All the above-mentioned studies revealed the same results as this study showed that workplace bullying has the positive relationship with psychological distress and job satisfaction with life satisfaction. On the other hand workplace, bullying and psychological distress have a significant negative relationship with levels of job satisfaction and life satisfaction.

Workplace Bullying as a Predictor of Psychological Distress:

The second hypothesis of the study is that workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of psychological distress among teachers in Sialkot City. The results (Table 4) of linear regression showed that workplace bullying was a strong predictor of psychological distress as the value of R^2 indicated that psychological distress was 39% affected by workplace bullying. Results further

revealed that there was significant impact of workplace bullying on psychological distress ($\beta = .62$, $t = 13.26$, $p < .001$). A study conducted by Nielsen, Hetland, Matthiesen, and Einarsen (2012), which supported this findings that bullying was a significant predictor of the psychological distress among employees. A similar finding was reported by Bernotaite and Malinauskiene's (2017), study that workplace bullying has a significant impact on the level of psychological distress.

Workplace Bullying as Predictor of Job Satisfaction: The third hypothesis was that workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of job satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. The R^2 showed that 24% workplace bullying was effected on the level of job satisfaction among teachers. Results (table 5) also revealed that workplace bullying was negatively affect the overall job satisfaction ($\beta = -.49$, $t = -9.39$, $p < .001$). A similar finding was reported in Francis (2014), that there was a negative impact of workplace bullying on the job satisfaction of employees. Further, Malik and Bano (2016), investigated a negative impact of workplace bullying on job satisfaction.

Workplace Bullying as Predictor of Life Satisfaction: The fourth hypothesis of the study was that workplace bullying would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. As a result of linear regression analysis, (table 6) the R^2 displayed that 9% life satisfaction was affected by workplace bullying. Moreover, the findings also revealed a significant negative impact of workplace bullying on life satisfaction ($\beta = -.30$, $t = -5.13$, $p < .001$). The research of Visinskaite (2015), also reported the same findings that workplace bullying was negatively affected the employee's life satisfaction. Similarly, Tolentino (2016), investigated a negative impact of workplace bullying on life satisfaction of teachers.

Psychological Distress as Predictor of Job Satisfaction: The fifth hypothesis was that psychological distress would be the significant predictor of job satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. The results (table 7) showed that 19% of job satisfaction level was affected by psychological distress. Findings further indicated that there is a

negative impact of psychological distress on job satisfaction ($\beta = -.43$, $t = -7.95$, $p < .001$).

The research of Amati et al., (2010), revealed a significant negative impact of psychological distress on the level of job satisfaction among nurses. Another study was conducted by Okwaraji and Aguwa (2015), also reported the same results that psychological distress was negatively affected by the job satisfaction of teachers.

Psychological Distress as Predictor of Life Satisfaction: The sixth hypothesis was that psychological distress would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. The R^2 demonstrated that life satisfaction was 10% affected by psychological distress. Furthermore, the results (table 8) shown a significant negative impact of psychological distress on life satisfaction ($\beta = -.33$, $t = -5.73$, $p < .001$).

The results of Abdullah and Mushtaq (2015), study demonstrated a negative effect of psychological distress on the level of life satisfaction of teachers. The similar results were reported by the research of Sharma and Garg (2016), that psychological distress was negatively predicted the life satisfaction.

Job Satisfaction as Predictor of Life Satisfaction: The seventh hypothesis of the study is that job satisfaction would be the significant predictor of life satisfaction among teachers in Sialkot City. The R^2 indicated that job satisfaction effects 11% overall life satisfaction among teachers. The results (table 9) show that job satisfaction was a strong predictor of life satisfaction ($\beta = .34$, $t = 6.00$, $p < .001$).

A similar finding was reported in the Banerjee's (2015), research that job satisfaction was positively predicting the life satisfaction. Another study of Alghamdi (2015), revealed a significant positive impact of job satisfaction on the level of life satisfaction of employees.

Major Conclusions and Findings: Following are the major findings and conclusions of the research study:

a. It has been found or concluded that workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction are significantly correlated. Results further demonstrated that there

is a positive relationship between workplace bullying and psychological distress. Moreover, job satisfaction also has a positive correlation with life satisfaction among teachers.

b. Workplace bullying and psychological distress were found negatively correlated with job satisfaction and life satisfaction of teachers.

c. The study concluded that workplace bullying and psychological distress are significant predictors of lower job satisfaction and reduced life satisfaction of teachers. It has also been concluded that workplace bullying is a strong predictor of psychological distress while job satisfaction is a strong predictor of life satisfaction.

Implications of the Study: The present research study has following implications: -

a. The current study provided a useful data that enhances the understanding of an individual and organization about the relationship of workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction.

b. This study offered a new idea in the domain of organizational research by opening up an open discussion on the issue of workplace bullying that further helps to understand the degree of intensity regarding physical damages and psychological ordeals of teachers as employees.

c. Additionally, this study highlights the impact of workplace bullying and psychological distress on the levels of job satisfaction and life satisfaction of teachers that are harmful for the individuals concerned and may lead to losses for the organization as well.

d. The findings of the study might be helpful for organizations to consider workplace bullying as a major source of mental health problems, lower job satisfaction and reduced life satisfaction of employees.

e. The research study offers suggestions for the organization to undertake measures to reduce workplace bullying for improving workers health and job satisfaction that can enhance employees performance and organization production. The concern authorities of the institutions should provide better working environment to teachers which must be free from bullying behaviors so that

they can have better health and achieve high level of job satisfaction as well as life satisfaction.

f. Study further provided a new translated version of Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R) in Urdu language to evaluate the degree of workplace bullying. This Urdu version of Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R will help many other researchers in future because earlier on Urdu version of NAQ-R was not available in Sialkot and Pakistan.

Limitations of the Study: Following are the limitations of the study: -

a. Since this study was conducted at Sialkot City and a sample of 270 teachers was selected as representative sample of teachers' population, therefore, it has limited generalization value.

b. The second limitation of the study is based on its purpose, which focused to investigate the relationship between the workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction, only the victims of bullying were included in the study. Those teachers who claimed that they were not the victims of workplace bullying, were excluded from the research study.

c. Another limitation is the order of the measures that may have affected the results of the study. As the first measure Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R) was related to the bullying experience of the participants that they faced in the last six months so therefore the perception of the participants about psychological distress and about their job satisfaction and life satisfaction may have changed during the past six months.

Suggestions: Following are the suggestions: -

1. A longitudinal study should be conducted to investigate cause and effect of workplace bullying, psychological distress, job satisfaction and life satisfaction.

2. Future studies should employ a larger sample even with different working groups such as doctors, bankers, nurses and factory employee etc.

3. Changing the order of measures may also be studied to find out the impact of order of exposure.

4. Future studies should be planned to explore the impact of sub-type of the workplace bullying

including work, person and physical related bullying. These researches should be conducted on the sub-scales of the measures.

5. Difference between types of institution and variables should be examined. Moreover, a different study should investigate the perpetrators of bullying.

6. Further research may explore organizational consequences of the variables such as overall level of production, work motivation and involvements etc.

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